

Refactoring the Logging and LoggerPluginInterface

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Associated Project Workitem

[Pull request for this feature Plugin Interface Repo](#)

Description

The primary motivation of this work was to develop a logger plugin system that would enable custom logging solutions for presenting workflow progress in different ways. These plugins would make it easier to debug workflows, monitor multiple simultaneous workflows, and provide cleaner, more informative output, addressing long-standing requests from the Snakemake community.

In order to implement the plugin system, a substantial refactoring of the existing Snakemake logging code was needed, as well as the implementation of a plugin interface so that logging plugins could seamlessly integrate with Snakemake. The existing logging system had accumulated technical debt over years of development, resulting in a complex and ad-hoc implementation that deviated from Python logging best practices. The architecture mixed multiple responsibilities within a single component, making it difficult to extend or customize logging behavior without modifying core Snakemake code.

In this series of changes, Snakemake's entire logging module has been refactored to more closely follow Python's standard logging recommendations. Notable changes and improvements are:

- Adopted Python logging standards: Replaced custom logging implementation with Python's built-in logging framework
- Structured workflow events: Introduced consistent event types for workflow start/finish, job updates, and progress tracking
- Simplified logging components: Separated filtering, formatting, and output handling into distinct, manageable parts

The logger plugin interface was designed and implemented to enable community-driven logging solutions. Key features include:

- Plugin interface creation: Developed a standardized way for external plugins to receive and process logging events
- Enhanced customization: Users can now create custom logging solutions without modifying Snakemake's core code

After the refactor and plugin interface were finalized, development of a logger plugin began during the hackathon to serve both as an example implementation and to provide a useful monitoring tool for the

community. `snkmt` (snakemate) was created as an interactive terminal user interface that demonstrates the capabilities of the new plugin system. The `snkmt logger plugin` writes workflow logs to a central SQLite database, which `snkmt` queries to provide real-time visualization of workflow progress, job status, and execution statistics in an intuitive terminal interface.

snkmt dashboard displaying real-time workflow progress and job status overview

Failed job dropdown providing detailed error information and debugging options

Log file modal showing detailed logs for individual failed jobs